

SkyCam: Ports Assets Defects detection system

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Abstract:

21 million tons is the total handling number of the third quarter at Sohar Port, with over 2200 chips received and more than 1900 companies operating within the port area (Eng.Sufyan ALMamari,2022). The numbers indicate that the port is growing, and the assets shall be consumed healthily. Marine fenders are equipment used to avoid collision between shapes and the marine. They are, and the other assets, inspected periodically to avoid any developments in their defects that may affect the port's operations. The current inspection process is manually examined by an inspector, which costs money, time, and staff harm. Based on the current system faces limitations that can be summarised in the following points:

1. The number of port assets is approximately 400+, which consumes time in the inspection process.
2. Manually inspection and data entry may be affected by human error.
3. Defects require analysis, assessment and classification is a tedious task that can be taken subjectively since it depends on personal judgement.

Statement of the Problem:

Currently, Sohar Port and Freezone is developing the framework of its smart city to increase operational efficiency, safety, and sustainability. We are introducing a novel method of detecting asset defects using a drone. The fundamental concept of the proposed system is to upload pictures at predetermined times. The captured images will be submitted to the suggested system, which will undergo automatic analysis.